

Prevalence of anti-Hsp27 antibodies and their relation to antisperm antibodies in infertile patients

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Abstract

Serum antibodies against the small heat shock protein Hsp27 (HspB1) have been associated with certain diseases but have not been studied in infertility. Sera from 73 infertile patients were tested for antisperm antibodies using agglutination and immobilization tests and ELISA, and for anti-Hsp27 antibodies using ELISA. Of these sera, 31 (42.5%) were positive for anti-Hsp27 antibodies, and 46 (63%) were positive for antisperm antibodies through analysis with at least one method. A total of 17 sera (23.3%) were positive for both anti-Hsp27 and antisperm antibodies. When sera containing both anti-Hsp27 and antisperm antibodies were used for immunofluorescence, the neck and tail of spermatozoa were stained, where the related sperm-specific protein HspB10 (ODF1) is localized. These data suggest that anti-Hsp27 antibodies are elevated in a certain proportion of infertile patients, which, in some of them, could be due to cross-reactivity between Hsp27 and the related sperm cytoskeletal component ODF1.

Keywords

antisperm antibodies, autoimmunity, Hsp27, infertility, spermatozoa

Introduction

Small heat shock proteins are low-molecular-weight chaperones characterized by a conserved alpha-crystallin domain. They recognize and bind non-native proteins, preventing their aggregation and facilitating their subsequent refolding by other chaperones such as Hsp70 (as lacking ATPase activity, small heat shock proteins cannot do the refolding themselves). Mammals have 10 small heat shock proteins (HspB1–HspB10) with different structures, tissue distributions, and functional specializations (Carra et al. 2017). HspB1, also known as Hsp27, is expressed in all types of muscles and many other tissues. It contributes to the stress

tolerance of cells and protects them from apoptosis (Singh et al. 2017). Anti-Hsp27 autoantibodies at low levels are present in the sera of healthy individuals, and their increase has recently been associated with certain conditions.

Elevated levels of anti-Hsp27 antibodies and Hsp27 itself have been reported in cancer, which could be explained by the upregulation of Hsp27 in tumors due to its anti-apoptotic activity (Homaei-Shandiz et al. 2016). Similar increases in both Hsp27 and the antibodies against it have been found in glaucoma, and glaucoma-like changes have been induced by immunization of rodent models with Hsp27 (Grotegut et al. 2020). Higher anti-Hsp27 antibody titers have also been detected in obesity (Kargari

et al. 2017). Anti-Hsp27 antibodies have been found to increase with age and hypertension (Shams et al. 2008) and to be elevated in acute coronary syndrome (Ghayour Mobarhan et al. 2008). Other authors, however, have found lower levels of Hsp27 and anti-Hsp27 antibodies in patients with cardiovascular disease compared to controls. They attributed the difference to the protective effect of anti-Hsp27 antibodies against inflammation and plaque formation and tested this hypothesis in a mouse model (Raizman et al. 2013; Shi et al. 2020).

To our knowledge, there are no published studies on anti-Hsp27 antibodies in infertility. It is known that Hsp27 is expressed both in maturing oocytes (Liu et al. 2010) and spermatogenic and Sertoli cells, despite being undetectable in mature spermatozoa (Biggiogera et al. 1996; Adly et al. 2008). The protective and antiapoptotic action of Hsp27 in the testis is thought to ameliorate the impact of stress and aging on spermatogenesis (Purandhar et al. 2014).

Infertility factors, by subjecting the gonads to stress, could be expected to increase Hsp27 expression in maturing gametes, but some of the above reports have instead documented its downregulation in certain infertility-associated pathologies, namely polycystic ovary syndrome (Liu et al. 2010) and spermatogenic maturation arrest (Adly et al. 2008). Notably, two other members of the small heat shock protein family, HspB9 and HspB10, have testis-specific expression. HspB9 is localized in spermatogonia, spermatocytes, and round spermatids, and HspB10 is localized in elongated spermatids and spermatozoa (Xun et al. 2015). The expression of HspB10 is consistent with its function because it, surprisingly, has been shown to be identical with ODF1, a structural component of sperm tail cytoskeletal elements known as outer dense fibers (Fontaine et al. 2003). The presence of small heat shock proteins specific for spermatogenic cells raises the question of the potential cross-reactivity of antibodies against them with Hsp27, or vice versa. If certain patients produce anti-Hsp27 antibodies, it is relevant to compare their prevalence to that of antisperm antibodies, a category of auto- and isoantibodies known to be associated with infertility (Gupta et al. 2022). To address these questions, we tested sera of infertile patients for the presence of anti-Hsp27 and antisperm antibodies.

Materials and methods

Study subjects

Sera of 73 patients (35 males and 38 females) with infertility, according to the World Health Organization criteria, who were referred to the Laboratory of Reproductive Immunology at the Department of Biology for antisperm antibody testing between 2022 and 2024, and control sera of age- and sex-matched healthy and fertile volunteers were used for this study. This research was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved

by the Institutional Review Board of the Medical University of Sofia (no. 1873/07.06.2022, based on protocol no. 09/23.05.2022). All subjects gave informed consent. The patients included 24 couples and 25 individuals who were tested without their partners. In most of them, infertility was unexplained, and therefore an immunological cause was suspected; in eight cases, another possible infertility factor had been identified in at least one of the partners (oligospermia, asthenozoospermia, varicocele, history of parotitis or cryptorchidism in males, or ovarian polycystosis in females), and in three more, another possible factor was suspected (history of prostatitis in a male and endometriosis in two females), but antisperm immunity was considered to be a likely contributing cause.

Venous blood samples (5 ml) were taken. Sera were obtained and heated to 56 °C for 30 min to inactivate endogenous complement.

Anti-Hsp27 antibody testing

Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) was used. Microplates were loaded with recombinant human Hsp27 (Elabsience), 0.45 µg/well, in 0.05 M carbonate-coating buffer (pH 9.6). After incubation at room temperature for 1 h and at 4 °C for 16–18 h, the plates were washed three times with washing buffer comprising phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), pH 7.2, with 0.05% Tween 20. Then, a blocking buffer based on PBS (pH 7.2) was applied (150 µl/well) for 60 min at room temperature. For blocking, 1% bovine serum albumin (BSA) and 0.2% Tween 20 were used. After that, patient and control sera diluted 1:20 in PBS (pH 7.2) were applied (50 µl/well) for 2 h at room temperature.

The plates were washed three times with washing buffer. Then, the second antibody (peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-human immunoglobulin, Santa Cruz Biotechnology) diluted 1:1000 in PBS (pH 7.2) was applied for 1 h at 37 °C in the dark. After washing three times with washing buffer, 0.05% o-phenylenediamine in citrate buffer (pH 5.0) with 0.15% H₂O₂ was applied for visualization. The reaction was stopped with 10% H₂SO₄ (50 µl/well). Optical densities (ODs) were measured using an ELISA reader DW-SM600 at 492 nm. An ELISA cut-off value of CO = $\bar{x} + 2$ SD was used, where \bar{x} was the mean value of OD for 13 control sera and SD the standard deviation. Sera with OD > CO were considered positive.

Antisperm antibody testing

Patient sera and a total of 112 control sera were applied to spermatozoa from healthy normozoospermic donors proven negative for antisperm antibodies. Three methods were used: ELISA, the tray agglutination test of Friberg (TAT), and the sperm immobilization test of Isojima (SIT). For ELISA, poly-L-lysine-coated microwell plates were loaded with swim-up sperm suspension (5×10^6 cells/ml, 50 µl/well), air-dried overnight at 37 °C, fixed with 30% methanol for 30 min at room temperature, washed three times with washing buffer, and processed as above.

TAT and SIT were performed as previously described (Dimitrova-Dikanarova et al. 2017). TAT was carried out in 60-well low-profile stacking trays (Robbins Scientific, Sunnyvale, CA, USA). Sera were applied in serial dilutions, and to each well, 1 μ l of swim-up sperm suspension (1×10^7 cells/ml) was added. After incubating trays for 1 h at 37 °C, agglutination was registered microscopically. Sera with agglutination titers ≥ 32 were considered positive.

For SIT, 60-well low-profile stacking trays (Robbins Scientific) were loaded with sera diluted 1:2 in Baker's buffer at 10 μ l/well. To each well, 1 μ l of swim-up sperm suspension (1×10^7 cells/ml) and 2 μ l of whole guinea-pig complement (National Center for Infectious and Parasitic Diseases, Sofia, Bulgaria) were added. Wells with inactivated complement served as negative controls. Trays were incubated for 1 h at 37 °C. Then, for each well, 100 sperm cells were examined, and the percentage of motile spermatozoa was calculated. The percentage for the negative control was divided by that of the test well to obtain its sperm immobilization value (SIV). Sperm immobilization values ≥ 2 were considered positive.

Statistics

The statistical significance of differences between patients and controls was evaluated using Fisher's exact test. The correlation between the anti-Hsp antibody and antisperm antibody positivity (detected using at least one method) was tested using Spearman's correlation coefficient through IBM SPSS Statistics 29.0. For the graphic presentation of the results, GraphPad Prism was used.

Immunofluorescence

Sera of different positivity statuses were used for immunofluorescence. Swim-up spermatozoa were washed with PBS, pH 7.2. They were air-dried on microscopic slides at room temperature and fixed with cold ethanol for 10 min and cold acetone for 2 min. The fixed samples were rehydrated for 10 min in PBS (pH 7.2) with 1% BSA. The same PBS with 1% BSA was used to dilute the antibodies and wash the slides after incubation with the antibodies. Rehydrated slides were incubated for 1 h at room temperature with patient or control sera (first antibody) diluted 1:20. A negative control was included with PBS with 1% BSA without serum. After washing twice for 10 min, FITC-conjugated second antibody (National Center for Infectious and Parasitic Diseases, Sofia, Bulgaria), diluted 1:50 together with 1 μ g/ml Hoechst 33342, was applied for 30 min at room temperature in the dark. The slides were washed twice for 10 min with PBS with 1% BSA and once with PBS. They were mounted for immunofluorescence in PBS/glycerol 1:9 (v/v) and observed using an Olympus BX53 fluorescent microscope.

Abbreviations

Hsp Heat shock protein;
ELISA Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay;

ODF Outer dense fibers;
PBS Phosphate-buffered saline;
BSA Bovine serum albumin;
OD Optical density;
CO cut-off;
SD Standard deviation;
TAT Tray agglutination test;
SIT Sperm immobilization test;
SIV Sperm immobilization value;
FITC Fluorescein isothiocyanate.

Results

Testing for anti-Hsp27 antibodies

Of the 73 sera from infertile patients, 31 (42.5%) were positive for anti-Hsp27 antibodies, although the differences between their values and the cut-off value were not large (Fig. 1). Of these patients, 18 were females and 13 were males. None of the control sera tested positive. The difference between patient and control groups was significant ($p < 0.01$).

Of the patients with underlying diagnoses, five men had anti-Hsp antibodies: one with asthenozoospermia, one with oligospermia, one with asthenozoospermia and a history of parotitis, one with varicocele, parotitis, and oligospermia, and one with isolated varicocele. Two were negative; they had histories of cryptorchidism and prostatitis, respectively. Three women were positive; two had ovarian polycystosis, and one had endometriosis. Another woman with endometriosis was negative. In total, out of the 11 patients with underlying diagnoses, eight were positive for anti-Hsp antibodies (73%). Of the patients without underlying diagnoses, 23 (37%) were positive (11 men and 12 women), and 39 were negative (17 men and 22 women). Thus, patients with underlying diagnoses were more likely to have anti-Hsp antibodies than patients without underlying diagnoses. This

Figure 1. Results of the detection of anti-Hsp27 antibodies using ELISA. Patients A are negative for antisperm antibodies and are shown as black circles, and patients B are positive for antisperm antibodies and are shown as white rhombs. Controls are shown as white circles. The controls were all negative for antisperm antibodies. OD, optical density.

difference was significant ($p < 0.05$). However, when men and women were analyzed separately, the statistical significance was lost due to the small numbers.

Testing for antisperm antibodies

The three applied methods for the detection of antisperm antibodies revealed 46 (of 73) patients (63%) and 10 (of 112) controls (9%) positive, as detected using at least one method. The difference between patients and controls was significant ($p < 0.0001$). Positive patients included 24 females and 22 males. The antisperm antibody positivity of these patients was detected through ELISA, TAT, and SIT (two sera); ELISA and TAT (eight sera); ELISA and SIT (seven sera); TAT and SIT (three sera); ELISA alone (18 sera); TAT alone (five sera); or SIT alone (three sera). The 10 positive control sera were positive using only one method.

A total of 17 sera (23%), from 10 females and seven males, were positive for both anti-Hsp27 and antisperm antibodies (Fig. 2). The antisperm antibody positivity of

Figure 2. Pie chart presenting the overlap between the presence of anti-Hsp27 and antisperm antibodies in the studied group of infertile patients.

these patients was detected using ELISA and TAT (three sera); ELISA and SIT (three sera); TAT and SIT (three sera); ELISA alone (six sera); or SIT alone (two sera).

There was no significant correlation between the presence of anti-Hsp antibodies and that of antisperm antibodies.

Immunofluorescent staining of spermatozoa

The immunofluorescent staining of spermatozoa with control sera and patient sera without significant antibody levels produced negative results. Sera positive for anti-Hsp27 antibodies only produced negative results or, in one case, weak staining in the equatorial segment, postacrosomal region, and tail. Sera positive for antisperm antibodies, with or without anti-Hsp27 antibodies, stained the sperm neck, tail, any of the three head domains, or some combination of these. Notably, three double-positive sera were tested by immunofluorescence, and all of them reacted with the neck and the tail (Fig. 3), although the same pattern was also observed in some of the antisperm antibody-positive, anti-Hsp27-negative sera.

Discussion

Because of the relatively small number of subjects tested, our study should be interpreted with caution. Nevertheless, the high proportion of infertile patients who tested positive for anti-Hsp27 antibodies is remarkable. The prevalence of these antibodies was comparable to that of antisperm antibodies, which are a common finding in infertility. We hypothesize that infertility is associated with gonadal stress, leading, on the one hand, to the elevated expression of Hsp27 in immature gametes and the somatic cells of the gonads and, on the other hand, to increased levels of death of these Hsp27-expressing cells, triggering the production of anti-Hsp27 antibodies. This supposition is supported by the finding that men with identified varicocele and/or abnormalities in their ejaculate and women with polycystosis tested positive. In this respect, there are intriguing reports of higher levels of anti-Hsp27 antibodies in patients with endometrial and cervical cancer (Bodzek et al. 2021), as

Figure 3. Human spermatozoa stained using human sera followed by FITC-labeled antihuman antibody (Ser), Hoechst 33342 (Chr), and the two images combined (Comb). **A.** Negative result produced by a control serum; **B.** Staining of the neck and the tail produced by a patient serum positive for both anti-Hsp27 and antisperm antibodies. Scale bars: 10 μm .

well as the presence of Hsp27 and its phosphorylated form in the spermatozoa of smokers (Henriques et al. 2023).

Another noteworthy result is the immunofluorescent staining of the sperm neck and tail by sera positive for both antisperm and anti-Hsp27 antibodies. These regions contain a sperm-specific small heat shock protein, HspB10 (ODF1). It is present in outer dense fibers, cytoskeletal elements that are resistant to factors damaging other sperm cell components (Markova 2001, 2004; Markova et al. 2011), and is therefore expected to persist after the death of the cells containing it as a likely trigger of auto- or isoimmune responses. This could imply immunological cross-reactivity between Hsp27 (HspB1) and the related sperm-specific component HspB10 in some infertile patients, although this phenomenon and its implications require further studies. It is possible that in a subset of patients, the immune response is actually directed against HspB10, and the positivity of anti-Hsp27 represents a cross-reaction. Studying a larger group of patients for both anti-Hsp27 and anti-HspB10 antibodies would reveal the relationship between these serum antibodies and their presence in patients of both sexes. Small Hsps (HspB1–HspB10) have similar conservative structures, consisting of an alpha-crystallin domain (ACD) flanked by variable C-terminal and N-terminal domains (Tedesco et al. 2022). Our previous research has found an increased prevalence of antibodies against another small heat shock protein, alpha-crystallin (HspB4 and HspB5), in patients with certain organ-specific autoimmune disorders (Buteva-Hristova et al. 2017).

Conclusion

Our study showed elevated levels of anti-Hsp27 antibodies in a proportion of infertile patients with unexplained infertility and suspected auto/isoimmune etiology. Sera positive for both antisperm and anti-Hsp27 antibodies stained the neck and tail of spermatozoa, suggesting possible cross-reactivity between Hsp27 and the related sperm cytoskeletal component ODF1.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Institutional Review Board (or Ethics Committee) of Medical University of Sofia (no. 1873/07.06.2022 based on protocol no. 09/23.05.2022) Informed consent was obtained from all the subjects involved in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

K. Kavaldzhieva – conceptualization, investigation, visualization, writing; D. Dimitrova-Dikanarova – conceptualization, investigation, supervision; A. Kolarov – investigation, statistics; D. Dinev – investigation; V. Lazarov – investigation; N. Mladenov – conceptualization, investigation, supervision, writing.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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